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Impact of genomic selection on genetic diversity in 5 local European cattle breeds

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ABSTRACT

Genomic selection (GS) has revolutionized animal breeding and accelerated genetic gains in breeding programs. Although GS has become common in cosmopolitan dairy cattle breeds, its implementation in local breeds has begun only more recently, or is still in progress. However, the introduction of GS in some cosmopolitan breeds has also been associated with increased inbreeding rates, raising concerns about the potential effects of GS on genetic diversity in smaller or local breeds. Our aim was to investigate the impact of GS on genetic diversity in 5 (small) local cattle breeds from 3 European countries: Meuse Rhine Yssel (MRY; from the Netherlands); Norwegian Red (NRC; from Norway); and Abondance (ABO), Tarentaise (TAR), and Vosgienne (VOS; from France). We investigated changes in population demographic structure, as well as trends and rates of kinship and inbreeding, using both pedigree- and genomic-based measures. The population size varied depending on the breed, with Vosgienne being the smallest and NRC being the largest. Single nucleotide polymorphism genotypes were available for 4,645 MRY, 193,489 NRC, 16,387 ABO, 8,578 TAR, and 4,472 VOS animals. Animals were genotyped with more than 40,000 SNPs. Overall, following the implementation of GS in these breeds, we observed a reduction of up to 4 years in generation intervals for sires, fewer calves that later became sires, and, for the French breeds, a broader sire usage. Such changes were likely due to GS enabling the preselection and screening of more young bulls. Additionally, the contributions of the top 10 sires were more evenly distributed after the introduction of GS. Although changes in inbreeding and kinship rates occurred after the introduction of GS, we found no consistent pattern across breeds: pedigree (and

genomic runs of homozygosity [ROH]-based) inbreeding rates per generation increased in MRY from -0.67 before GS to 0.51 after GS (from -1.12 to 0.93) and TAR from 0.35 to 0.93 (from 0.68 to 0.86), but decreased in NRC from 0.26 to 0.05 (from 0.10 to 0.06), Abondance from 1.19 to 0.99 (from 2.39 to 0.58), and Vosgienne from 0.53 to 0.23 (from 0.88 to 0.19). Moreover, analysis of genomic ROH-based inbreeding by length class showed that after the implementation of GS, the largest changes in inbreeding level and inbreeding rates per generation occurred for shorter ROH segments. Our study suggests that changes and increases in inbreeding rates may occur after the introduction of GS, although they may not be directly due to the introduction of GS per se, but rather due to population management strategies, such as optimal contribution selection. Our findings emphasize the importance of monitoring changes in both genetic diversity and population demographic structure after implementing GS in local breeds, as well as adjusting breeding strategies when needed to ensure long-term sustainability.

Key words: genetic diversity, inbreeding, genomic selection, local breeds

INTRODUCTION

The advent of genomic selection (GS; Nejati-Javaremi et al., 1997; Meuwissen et al., 2001) had a profound influence on cattle breeding (García-Ruiz et al., 2016; Meuwissen et al., 2016). For instance, the implementation of GS in cattle breeding programs increased selection accuracy; improved the pre-selection of young bulls, reducing the costs associated with progeny testing; increased selection intensity; and reduced generation intervals (Schaeffer, 2006; de Roos et al., 2011; Wiggans et al., 2017). These factors have led to higher genetic gains for traits of interest when implementing GS compared with traditional breeding schemes (Schaeffer, 2006; Hayes et al., 2013; Meuwissen et al., 2013; García-

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Ruiz et al., 2016). Genomic selection has now become common in popular cattle breeds, whereas local breeds recently started (or are in the process of) introducing GS (Pryce and Daetwyler, 2012; Wiggans et al., 2017; Interbull Centre, 2024). However, there has been concern about whether the higher selection intensity and faster turnover of generations brought by GS may also lead to increased mating of related individuals, especially in small populations, which would then result in faster loss of genetic diversity, increased inbreeding depression, and increased frequency of recessive deleterious mutations (Cole, 2015; Howard et al., 2017; Doekes et al., 2021). It is therefore essential to investigate and monitor the possible impact of implementing GS on the genetic diversity of local cattle breeds, as these breeds may present unique features in their management strategies and breeding programs compared with more popular ones.

Compared with pedigree-based selection, GS allows the estimation of Mendelian sampling terms, enabling the exploitation of within-family variation and potentially reducing the co-selection of family members (Daetwyler et al., 2007; Lillehammer et al., 2011). However, results from previous studies across several cattle breeds showed that genetic diversity may be affected by the introduction of GS. In Holstein, inbreeding rates increased since the introduction of GS in North America (Forutan et al., 2018; Makanjuola et al., 2020; Guinan et al., 2023), the Netherlands (Doekes et al., 2018), Poland (Topolski and Jagusiak, 2020), France (Doublet et al., 2019), Australia (Scott et al., 2021), and Italy (Ablondi et al., 2022). Similarly, Makanjuola et al. (2020) and Sarviaho et al. (2023) reported increases in inbreeding rates after the introduction of GS in Jersey and in Finnish Ayrshire, respectively. These increases were not only for rates of inbreeding on a yearly basis, which is expected due to the shortening of generation intervals when implementing GS (Pryce and Daetwyler, 2012), but also on a generational basis. On the other hand, similar increases in inbreeding rates were not observed for other breeds where GS has also been introduced, such as Normande and Montbéliarde (Doublet et al., 2019) and Aberdeen Angus (Lozada-Soto et al., 2021). In particular, Doublet et al. (2019) showed that the breeding scheme had an effect on the effect of GS on genetic diversity. Thus, the impact of the implementation of GS on the genetic diversity of cattle breeds may differ across breeds.

In the pre-genomics era, pedigree-based inbreeding was the only tool to assess genetic diversity, genetic drift, and inbreeding. Genomic data now offer new tools to further evaluate and assess inbreeding in cattle populations throughout their genome (Howard et al., 2017; Doekes et al., 2021). The aim of this study was to investigate, using both pedigree-based and genomic-based measures, the impact of GS on genetic diversity in local cattle popu-

lations. In particular, we investigated inbreeding rates before and after the introduction of GS in 5 (small) local European cattle breeds from 3 countries. These breeds have undergone GS for at least 4 years and differ both in population size and genetic management, allowing to investigate the impact of GS on inbreeding rates and loss of genetic diversity relative to each population's demographic structure (e.g., number of sires and dams, sires' contribution), which can vary significantly across local breeds.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The data analyzed in this study came from existing databases and was provided by the respective breed organizations. Thus, no animals were used in this study, and ethical approval for the use of animals was not necessary.

Data Available

Individual pedigree and genomic data were available for 5 local European cattle breeds across 3 countries: Meuse Rhine Yssel (MRY) from the Netherlands; Norwegian Red Cattle (NRC) from Norway; and Abondance (ABO), Tarentaise (TAR), and Vosgienne (VOS) from France (Figure 1). Table 1 reports an overview of the size of the datasets used for each breed, the years analyzed, and the year in which GS was introduced. We defined the year of the introduction of GS as the year in which genomic-based estimated breeding values were first made available to breeders. Hereafter, we provide a brief description of the breeds and describe the data preparation of each dataset.

Dutch Breed: Meuse Rhine Yssel Breed

Breed Description and Management. The MRV is a Dutch dual-purpose cattle breed that originates from the central region of the Netherlands, between the rivers Meuse, Rhine, and Yssel (Maas, Rijn, and IJssel, in Dutch), after which it is named. The MRV is a relatively small population (Hiemstra et al., 2010; Stoop et al., 2017; Eynard et al., 2018b) with ~5,000 calves born per year, and in which GS began in the late 2018 (CRV, 2018a). The genetic management of the MRV breed partially followed that of the Dutch Holstein-Friesian breed (Doekes et al., 2018; Bonifazi et al., 2022), with the breeding goal expanded around 2000 to include traits related to fertility, reproduction, and longevity. In general, the Dutch-Flemish total merit index (NVI) is reviewed every 5 years (CRV, 2022, 2024). From 2018 onward, CRV started using the dual purpose NVI for MRV instead of the dairy one (CRV, 2018b). The current dual-purpose NVI assigns weights of 34%, 42%, and 24% for produc-

Figure 1. Breeds investigated in this study: MRY from the Netherlands (© dierenbeeldbank), Norwegian Red from Norway (© Els Korsten), Abondance (© OS_RAR), Tarentaise (© OS Tarentaise), and Vosgienne (© OS Vosgienne) from France.

tion, functional traits, and conformation traits, respectively (see CRV, 2022 for more details).

Around the year 2000, the so-called “cold sire system” was introduced in MRY in order to maintain genetic diversity by increasing the number of sires used (Hiemstra and de Haas, 2004). In this system, ~10 young bulls are progeny tested per year, with each bull being culled when 20,000 doses of frozen semen have been collected. Although optimum contribution selection (OCS; Meuwissen, 1997) has not been formally implemented in MRY, some of its principles have been applied through the cold sire system and by ensuring that the progeny-tested bulls selected each year originated from different parents, thereby limiting coancestry among sires and restricting

the rate of inbreeding (Henk Geertsema, personal communication).

Data Preparation. Pedigree and genomic data were provided by CRV (<https://crv4all.com>). The pedigree included 205,933 animals born between 1910 and 2022 and was checked using the “OptiSel” R package (Wellmann, 2019) for absence of duplicates, pedigree loops, and inconsistencies in the sex of the parents. All animals in the pedigree had information on the year of birth. Before 1975, data were incomplete, and results on these years are not presented, although the full pedigree information was used for calculation of inbreeding and kinship coefficients. Genomic data were available in the form of individual SNP genotypes. Individuals were genotyped with

Table 1. Summary of data and information available in each breed: size of the pedigree, number of genotyped animals, interval of years analyzed, year of introduction of genomic selection, number of registered breeding females and males in 2022 (source: Domestic Animal Diversity Information System; FAO, 2025), and pedigree completeness (as complete generation equivalents) in the latest year analyzed

Breed	Pedigrees, n	Genotyped animals, n	Years analyzed	Introduction of genomic selection	Breeding females, n	Breeding males, n	Pedigree completeness
MRY	205,933	4,645	1975–2021	2018	8,068	77	9.94
Norwegian Red	5,125,148	193,489	1975–2022	2016	175,975	130 ¹	13.33
Abondance	833,109	16,387	2000–2020	2014	42,634	279	6.02
Tarentaise	279,333	8,578	2000–2020	2014	14,168	149	6.44
Vosgienne	101,490	4,472	2000–2020	2014	5,687	181	3.05

¹Latest recorded number as of 2015.

Illumina Eurogenomics arrays (v1 to v4.1; Eurogenomics), and missing genotypes were imputed using FImpute (Sargolzaei et al., 2014). A total of 44,645 autosomal markers for 4,645 purebred MRY animals (i.e., with a pedigree-based breed composition for MRY $\geq 87.5\%$) were available. The SNP panel was checked for the absence of duplicated SNPs (one duplicated SNP removed). Further quality controls on genomic data were performed using Plink v1.9 (Chang et al., 2015), and SNPs with minor allele frequency lower than 0.01 were discarded (3,685 SNPs removed). After these edits, 4,645 animals and 40,959 SNP remained for subsequent analyses (Table 1).

Norwegian Breed: Norwegian Red Breed

Breed Description and Management. The NRC cattle breed, locally known as Norsk Rødt Fe, originated in Norway around 1930. Assuming a sex ratio of 0.5, the number of calves born per year is $\sim 100,000$. As such, NRC was the largest breed analyzed in this study (Table 1). Mating decisions in NRC were based on the relationships between the parents and their estimated breeding values. The breeding goal weighs milk production traits by 23%, beef production traits by 7%, and functional traits by 70% (Norwegian Red, 2025). The overall inbreeding was monitored and when needed reduced by selecting more sires with lower pedigree relationships. From 2010 onward, the genetic management has increasingly used the mating proportions recommended by OCS to guide selection decisions, with OCS being based on pedigree-based relationships. For NRC, GS started in 2016. After the introduction of GS, genomic estimated breeding values have been used for selection, whereas OCS is based on pedigree-based relationships. Mating advice is increasingly based on genomic relationships where available. Before GS, ~ 100 young bulls were progeny tested annually, of which ~ 15 were selected to be artificial insemination (AI) sires.

Data Preparation. The pedigree included 5,125,148 animals born between 1900 and 2024. Individual genotypes were available for a panel of 45,255 SNPs on 193,489 animals (minor allele frequency > 0.01). Missing genotypes were imputed using FImpute (Sargolzaei et al., 2014). These imputed genotypes were a subset of a larger dataset of imputed genotypes used in routine breeding value evaluations, where the actual genotypes came from different platforms: a customized Affymetrix 55k SNP chip (Affymetrix, Santa Clara, CA), Illumina BovineSNP50 BeadChip v1 and v2 (Illumina, San Diego, CA), Illumina BovineHD Genotyping BeadChip (Illumina, San Diego, CA) and Affymetrix 25k (Affymetrix, Santa Clara, CA). Finally, results for NRC are presented up to and including 2022 for consistency between results

based on genomic data (available until 2022) and those based on pedigree.

French Breeds: Abondance, Tarentaise, Vosgienne

Breed Description and Management. Abondance, TAR, and VOS are all French cattle breeds adapted to mountain conditions. These local breeds are essential to the preservation of mountain regions and are linked to the production of numerous Protected Designation of Origin French cheeses, making them profitable despite their lower milk production compared with cosmopolitan breeds.

Abondance, originally from Haute-Savoie, is a dairy breed renowned for its milk, which is used in the production of cheeses such as Reblochon or Abondance. Abondance is the fourth French dairy cattle breed in terms of population size with about 43,000 live cows (Institut de l'Élevage, 2022), albeit it represents only 1.3% of the total French dairy cattle population. With over 25,000 calves born per year, ABO was the second largest breed analyzed in this study. The breed originates from the French Alps, where it usually grazes on pasture, and it is well adapted to high altitudes ($> 2,000$ m). The ABO breed is mainly a free-range breed even if it is raised indoors during the winter season due to the rigorous conditions in the mountains. Cows produce $\sim 6,000$ kg of milk per year. The mean herd size of this breed is ~ 20 cows. Reproduction is almost exclusively conducted with AI. The selection nucleus consists of 1,261 farms and 21,000 cows (equivalent to 38% of the total population). Each year, ~ 20 AI sires are selected, and GS started in 2014. Until 2025, the ABO total merit index (ISU in French) consisted of 50% weight dedicated to milk production, 20% to conformation, 9% to udder health, 15.5% to fertility, and 5.5% to longevity (AgroParisTech, 2025a).

Tarentaise is a dairy breed also originating and grazing in the Alps, whose milk is used to make alpine cheeses, such as Beaufort. It is often found in the same area as ABO and raised under the same conditions: mainly free-range, except during winter. As for ABO, feeding mainly relies on hay when indoors, and silage is usually not used. It produces $\sim 4,800$ kg of milk per year per cow. Its live population size consists of $\sim 14,000$ live cows (Institut de l'Élevage, 2022), and with $\sim 9,500$ calves born per year, its population size is intermediate among the 5 breeds analyzed in this study. Abondance has a selection nucleus of 424 farms including 7,700 cows (equivalent to 59% of the total population). Each year, 18 AI sires are selected. For TAR, until 2008, the total merit index (TMI) consisted of weights of 46% for milk production, 16% for conformation, 16% for udder health, 16% for fertility, and 6% for longevity. From 2018, the TMI weights changed to 35% for milk production, 10% for

conformation, 17.5% for udder health, 17.5% for fertility, 15% for longevity, and 5% for milking speed (Institut de l'Élevage, 2018).

Vosgienne, originally from the Vosges mountain area, is a dual-purpose breed known for its ability to efficiently utilize poor-quality and marginal pastures, and whose milk is used in the production of the Munster cheese. Vosgienne is selected for both milk and meat, with cows producing ~4,200 kg of milk per year. The VOS consists of a small French population located in the eastern Vosges massif. With <4,000 calves born per year, VOS is the least numerous breed analyzed in this study. As with the other mountainous local French breeds, it is raised free-range, except during winter. The population consists of ~10,000 live cows in total, with only 4 to 6 AI sires selected each year (Organisme de sélection de la Race Vosgienne; OS Vosgienne personal communication). The selection nucleus consists of 79 farms and 1,400 cows (equivalent to 15% of the total population). All VOS animals are genotyped, making it the only breed in France to fall into such situation. Finally, since 2005, the Vosgienne TMI assigns 50% weight to milk production, 25% to conformation, 15% to udder health, and 10% to fertility (AgroParisTech, 2025b).

Data Preparation. The ABO pedigree included 833,109 animals born between 1946 and 2021, making it the largest breed among the French ones analyzed (Table 1). The TAR pedigree included 279,333 animals born between 1949 and 2021. Finally, the VOS pedigree included a total of 101,490 animals born between 1950 and 2021 (Table 1).

For the 3 French breeds, individual genotypes were available at ~50K SNPs or were imputed to ~50K. A standard imputation procedure is applied to all genotyped animals regardless of the genotyping array used (low-density 10K SNPs, medium-density 50K SNPs, high-density 600K SNPs, sequence) to make them comparable into the French national database. The number of genotyped animals was 16,387, 8,578, and 4,472, for ABO, TAR, and VOS, respectively (Table 1). First, genotyped individuals for the 3 French breeds were imputed (within-breed imputation) using FImpute (Sargolzaei et al., 2014) for 53,469 common SNPs of the Illumina Bovine BeadChip, resulting in no missing genotype data for the 3 breeds and an SNP genotyping rate of 100%. Next, a filter was applied to remove only monomorphic SNPs (i.e., fixed in one breed), leading to a remaining 51,309 SNPs in ABO, 49,046 SNPs in TAR, and 51,005 SNPs in VOS. Only genotypes of animals born from 2012 onward were considered in order to obtain a representative picture of the whole population because from this date, a large majority of the animals were genotyped in each of the 3 French breeds. Finally, GS started in 2014 in all 3 French breeds.

Population Demographic Structure and Statistics

Population demographic structure and other related statistics were obtained based on pedigree data using Retriever software (Windig and Hulsege, 2021). Pedigree completeness was assessed by computing the average number of complete generation equivalents (CGE) per year (Maignel et al., 1996). For each individual i ,

CGE was defined as the sum of $\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^n$, over all known an-

cestors that can be traced back in its pedigree in both the paternal and maternal line, and n being the number of generations between the individual i and its ancestor. For all breeds, CGE increased over time (Supplemental Figure S2, see Notes). The average CGE for animals born in the last year was: 9.94, 13.33, 6.02, 6.44, and 3.05, for MRY, NRC, ABO, TAR, and VOS, respectively (Table 1). The average generation interval (L) per year, defined as the average age of the parent(s) at birth of their offspring, was computed for sires, dams, and both parents. To quantify the size of the population involved in breeding and its changes over time, we computed for each year the number of male and female born calves, which later appeared as sires and dams, respectively, in the pedigree. We excluded calves that did not appear in the pedigree as a sire or dam because, especially in early years for males, these animals tend to not be registered, giving the false impression of a smaller population size. Additionally, one of the main causes of high inbreeding rates is a few popular males that sire a large proportion of the calves. Therefore, we analyzed the number of bulls that sired calves each year and the average number of calves born per sire. Moreover, we investigated the skewness in sires' contributions by quantifying changes in the contribution of the 10 most used sires within a specific year to the total number of offspring born in that same year. The top 10 sires' contributions were expressed as percentages.

Pedigree-Based and Genomic-Based Measures of Genetic Diversity

Pedigree-Based Measures. Pedigree-based measures of genetic diversity were computed using Retriever software (Windig and Hulsege, 2021). These measures were calculated using the whole pedigree and averaged per year. Inbreeding coefficients for each animal in the pedigree (F_{PED}) were calculated following Meuwissen and Luo (1992). Kinship coefficients (f_{PED}) between all animals born in the same year were calculated following Sargolzaei et al. (2005). Average f_{PED} were computed without self-kinship for all animals in the pedigree, and for animals later becoming sire or dam.

ROH-Based Inbreeding. For genotyped animals, genomic inbreeding based on runs of homozygosity (**ROH**; F_{ROH}) was calculated. Runs of homozygosity were detected using Plink v1.9 (Chang et al., 2015) and analyzed using the “detectRUNS” R package (Biscarini et al., 2019). The following Plink parameters were used to estimate ROH: *-homozyg-window-snp 15, -homozyg-gap 150, -homozyg-snp 15, -homozyg-density 75, -homozyg-kb 1000*. Thus, ROH were defined using a scanning window of 15 consecutive homozygotes SNP. Runs of homozygosity must have had a maximum gap between 2 SNPs of 150 kb, a minimum of 15 SNP, a minimum of one SNP per 75 kb, and a minimum length of 1,000 kb. These parameters follow those described by Doublet et al. (2019) for 3 French dairy cattle breeds with genotyping densities similar to the ones used in this study. Next, the F_{ROH} for individual i was calculated as the proportion of genome in ROH (McQuillan et al., 2008) as

$$F_{ROH_i} = \frac{\sum_{m=1}^{n_{ROH_i}} L_{ROH_{i,m}}}{L_{auto}}$$

where n_{ROH_i} is the total number of ROH in individual i , $L_{ROH_{i,m}}$ is the length of the m th ROH, and L_{auto} is the total length of the autosome covered by SNPs. Furthermore, the average number of ROH, their average lengths, and the average length of the genome covered by ROH was computed per individual.

Shorter ROH are expected to reflect more ancient inbreeding, whereas longer ROH are expected to reflect more recent inbreeding (Broman and Weber, 1999; McQuillan et al., 2008). Therefore, to gain insights into ancient and recent inbreeding, the identified ROH were divided into 5 k classes based on their length: [1–2), [2–4), [4–8), [8–16), and ≥ 16 Mb. For example, the class “[1–2) Mb” includes ROH ranging from 1 Mb (included) up to 2 Mb (excluded) of length. The approximate number of ancestral generations captured by the ROH classes 1–2, 2–4, 4–8, 8–16, and ≥ 16 was estimated to be ~ 50 –25, ~ 25 –12.5, ~ 12.5 –6, ~ 6 –3, and < 3 generations ago, respectively. These estimates were obtained following Doekes et al. (2018), assuming that the length of an ROH originating from a common ancestor G generation ago follows an exponential distribution with mean of $1/2G$ Morgans (Browning, 2008; Speed and Balding, 2015), and a mean genetic distance of 1 Morgan per 100 Mb (Ma et al., 2015) with uniform recombination rates across the genome and across sexes. Doekes et al. (2019, Figure 2) reports a more detailed expectation of the age of inbreeding for each ROH class. The average distribution per individual of the total genome in each ROH class was computed. Furthermore, inbreeding coefficients were calculated for each ROH class k (F_{ROH_k}) as

$$F_{ROH_k} = \frac{\sum_{m=1}^{n_{ROH_k}} L_{ROH_{k,m}}}{L_{auto}}$$

where n_{ROH_k} is the total

number of ROH in class k in individual i , $L_{ROH_{k,m}}$ is the length of the m th ROH of class k , and L_{auto} is the total length of the autosome covered by SNPs.

GRM-Based Inbreeding. As a measure of marker homozygosity, genomic inbreeding based on the genomic relationship matrix (**GRM**; F_{GRM}) was computed for genotyped animals. The GRM was constructed following

VanRaden's (2008) method 1 as
$$\mathbf{GRM} = \frac{\mathbf{ZZ}'}{2 \sum_{j=1}^m p_j (1 - p_j)}$$
,

where \mathbf{Z} is the centered matrix of genotypes for all genotyped individuals across all loci (m); Z_{ij} is equal to $\mathbf{M}_{ij} - 2p_j$, with \mathbf{M}_{ij} being the genotype for individual i (coded as 0, 1, and 2 for the homozygote, heterozygote, and alternative homozygote) at locus j ; and p is the allele frequency at locus j . Allele frequencies were fixed at $p_j = 0.5$ for all loci. The GRM-based genomic inbreeding coefficients (F_{GRM}) for individual i was computed as $F_{GRM_i} = \mathbf{G}_{i,i} - 1$, with $\mathbf{G}_{i,i}$ being the diagonal GRM element for individual i . Fixing allele frequencies at 0.5 gives equal weight to all markers and is expected to improve the comparability of results across breeds, as well as the consistency between the 2 genomic-based coefficients, F_{ROH} and F_{GRM} (Callegaro et al., 2025). With such construction, F_{GRM} is equivalent to the genome-wide proportion of homozygous SNPs, with a scaling difference (i.e., twice the individual's homozygosity; Eynard et al., 2016; Doekes et al., 2018). The F_{GRM} was computed using “calc_grm” software (Calus and Vandenplas, 2016) for MRY and French breeds, and “gghatvr4” software for NRC (Meuwissen, 2023).

Rates of Kinship and Inbreeding. Annual and generational rates of kinship and inbreeding were computed for each breed for specific intervals of years based on the observed major breakpoints in pedigree-based inbreeding trends and the year of introduction of GS. For MRY, these periods were 1975–2000, 2000–2013, 2013–2019, and 2019–2021. For NRC, the defined periods were 1975–2000, 2000–2010, 2010–2016, and 2016–2020. Finally, for ABO, TAR, and VOS, the defined periods were 2000–2014 and 2014–2020, corresponding to progeny testing and genomic evaluations periods, respectively. Annual rates of kinship (f_{PED}) and inbreeding for F_{PED} , F_{ROH} , and F_{GRM} coefficients were computed following Pérez-Enciso (1995), specifically, as -1 times the slope of the regression of $\ln(1 - \bar{x})$ on the year of birth, with \bar{x} being the average value of either f_{PED} , F_{PED} , F_{ROH} , and F_{GRM} per year. Thus, the fitted model was

$$\ln(1 - \bar{x}_i) = b_0 + b_1 \cdot year_i + e_i,$$

where b_0 is the intercept, b_1 is the slope associated with year of birth i , and e is the residual term. The annual rate of kinship or inbreeding is defined as $-b_1$. This approach accounts for the fact that kinship and inbreeding are not linear and asymptotes to 1. Furthermore, inbreeding rates per generation were obtained by multiplying the annual rates of kinship or inbreeding by the average generation interval of both parents in the years considered. Therefore, we computed both annual and generational rates of kinship and inbreeding. All rates were expressed as percentages. It should be noted that, hereafter, we will use the symbol Δ only to refer to generational rates. Therefore, the terms Δf and ΔF refer only to kinship and inbreeding rates per generation, respectively. Finally, the estimated effective population size (N_e) was computed as $N_e = \frac{1}{2 \cdot \Delta F}$ (Falconer and Mackay, 1996), with ΔF being the generational inbreeding rate of F_{PED} , F_{ROH} , or F_{PED} .

Software Availability. The Retriever software (Windig and Hulsege, 2021) is accessible at <https://genbankdata.cgn.wur.nl/software/Retriever/Retriever.html>. The R functions used to process the outputs of Retriever have been made available in the “labradoR” R package (<https://github.com/bonifazi/labradoR>).

RESULTS

Hereafter, we first present the results on the population demographic structure for the 5 breeds, followed by the results on genetic diversity measures.

Population Demographic Structure

Population Size. Across breeds, the number of male and female calves that later became sires and dams, respectively, fluctuated across the years analyzed but remained overall rather constant, with the exception of MRY and NRC (Figure 2). The VOS was the smallest breed, with ~20 male and ~600 female calves that later became parent born per year between 2010 and 2015. This was followed by TAR (~50 male calves and 2,600 female calves between 2010 and 2015), MRY (~90 and 1,600 female calves between 1990 and 2015) and ABO (~150 male calves and 7,000 female calves between 2010 and 2015). The NRC had the largest population size, with ~650 male calves and 50,000 female calves later becoming parent between 2010 and 2015. For MRY, the number of calves born per year that later became sires constantly decreased over time: from 367 in 1975 to 85 in 2018 (Figure 2). For NRC, the number of calves that later become sires was stable at ~400 per year between 1975 up to 2010, except for a sharp increase at around the years 2000 and 2001. From 2009 onward, the number

of calves that later become sires increased again at ~600 per year. These changes are caused by a difference in the registration procedure of bulls involved in natural mating and do not reflect an actual increase in the use of sires. The decrease observed in the most recent years for the number of male and female calves that later become sires and dams, respectively, is expected because animals generally are too young to have become parents yet. However, the total number of calves born and registered in this time was rather constant (Supplemental Figure S3, see Notes).

The number of sires used per year decreased over time for MRY, whereas it increased for NRC and French breeds. For MRY, the number of sires used in each year decreased from 607 in 1975 to 362 in 2005 (Figure 3), overall remaining stable in the years before and after the implementation of GS (on average 360.3 between 2005 and 2021). For NRC, the number of sires used in each year gradually decreased from 1975 to 2000 (908 and 547, respectively). From 2000, the number of sires used increased up to 2015 (1,209 sires), with 2 sharp increases in 2001–2002 and in 2011. These increases are due to a more detailed registration of natural mating NRC sires on commercial farms. However, after the implementation of GS, the number of sires used in NRC started to decrease, moving from 1,150 in 2016 to 872 in 2022 (Figure 3). This decline is attributed to a decrease in the number of natural mating sires, following a general trend toward reduced use of such sires. Although natural mating sires dominate the number of sires that have offspring, their total number of offspring is small compared with that of AI sires, and their offspring are rarely selected as parents (i.e., their contribution to the genetic improvement of the NRC population is small). The recent reduction in the use of natural mating sires has been accompanied by a corresponding increase in the number of calves born per sire (Supplemental Figure S1, see Notes). Finally, for all 3 French breeds, the number of sires used each year increased over time, even after the introduction of GS (Figure 3): from 288, 122, and 44 in 2000 to 437, 177, and 69 in 2014, and to 449, 168, and 100 in 2020, for ABO, TAR, and VOS, respectively. Thus, after the introduction of GS, the number of sires used remained stable (MRY and TAR), decreased (NRC), or increased (ABO and VOS).

Generation Interval. Overall, the average age of dams at time of calving was more or less constant over time in all 5 breeds, even after the implementation of GS (Figure 4). In general, the dams' generation interval was close to 5 yr or slightly above for all breeds except for NRC, for which it was ~3.5 yr. Compared with dams, generation intervals for sires were less stable (Figure 4). For MRY, the sires' generation interval fluctuated over time and was, on average, 6.8 yr across the whole period

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Figure 2. Number of males becoming sires and females becoming dams in each year of birth. Vertical blue lines indicate the year of onset of genomic selection. The last 3 (for MRY) or 2 (other breeds) years were removed as males and females are still young to be used as parents.

Figure 3. Number of sires used in each year. Vertical blue lines indicate the year of onset of genomic selection.

of 1975 to 2021, showing a small decrease before the implementation of GS and then a slight increase afterward (on average 7.8, 6.7, 6.3, and 6.6 yr in 1975–1980, 1981–2015, 2015–2018, and 2019–2020, respectively). For NRC, the sire generation interval was on average 5.5 yr between 1975 up to the introduction of GS in 2016, after which it strongly decreased to close to 3 yr from 2018 onward (average of 2.9 yr between 2018 and 2022). For ABO, the sires' generation interval slightly increased up to the introduction of GS (7.4 to 8.9 yr in 2000 and 2014, respectively), after which it decreased to 4.9 yr in 2020. For TAR, the sires' generation interval fluctuated before the introduction of GS, with values above 7.5 yr (maximum of 8.5 yr in 2010), and then decreased afterward to 4.2 yr in 2020. In VOS, sires' generation interval increased from 7.4 yr in 2000 to 10.4 yr in 2015, remaining at this high level for 3 yr after the introduction of GS, and then decreasing to 8.5 yr in 2020. Thus, sires' generation intervals clearly decreased in all breeds after the introduction of GS, except for the MRY.

Skewness of Sires' Contributions. For all breeds, the total contribution of the top 10 sires reduced in recent years (Figure 5). For MRY, the contribution of the top

10 MRY sires increased from around 28% in 1975 to over 46% in 1996 (Figure 5), after which it decreased, up to ~34% in the years after the implementation of GS (2019–2021). Similarly, for NRC, the contribution of the top 10 sires first increased to over 50% in 2014, after which it decreased, especially in the years after the introduction of GS, down to ~28% in 2022. For both MRY and NRC, the contributions within the top 10 sires were quite even in the last years, whereas in the years around 2000, the contributions were far more skewed, with the top 3 sires taking close to or more than half of the top 10 sires' contributions (on average 51.7% and 43.5% for the 2000–2015 period for MRY and NRC, respectively). Likewise, for the French breeds, the contribution of the top 10 sires reduced and became more even after the introduction of GS. Overall, French breeds showed a high contribution of the top 10 sires. Despite being the largest of the French breed analyzed, the contribution of the top 10 sires in ABO were above 50% up to 2015 (54.8% on average for the 2000–2015 period; Figure 5). Two years after the introduction of GS, the contribution of the top 10 sires strongly reduced to 29.6% on average for the 2016–2020 period. For TAR, the pattern was similar to

Figure 4. Generation intervals trends for sires, dams, and both parents. Y-axes report the number of years. Vertical blue lines indicate the year of onset of genomic selection.

ABO; the contribution of the top 10 sires was 50.9% on average for the 2000–2015 period, and then reduced to 31.9% for the 2016–2020 period. Among all breeds, VOS had the highest contribution of the top 10 sires, with values above 65% and close to 75% in the 2000–2011 period (average of 70.1% and 68.0% for the 2000–2011 and 2000–2014 periods, respectively). Such high contributions for VOS were expected given the limited population size and number of selected AI sires per year. After 2012, the contribution of the top 10 sires in VOS started to reduce and was below 50% from 2018 onward (51.8% and 48.9% on average for the 2014–2020 and 2016–2020 periods, respectively). Finally, for all breeds, several top sires contributed offspring across multiple consecutive years, indicating a sustained usage over time. Overall, the observed reduction in all breeds of the contribution of the top 10 sires happened either before (MRY) or after (NRC and French breeds) the start of GS.

Genetic Diversity

Pedigree-Based Measures. Trends of pedigree-based inbreeding and their corresponding annual and generational rates (ΔF_{PED}) varied according to the breed considered. For MRY, F_{PED} increased from 1975 up to 2013, decreased after 2013 up to 2019, and finally increased again in 2020 and 2021 (Figure 6). Before the introduction of GS, rates of F_{PED} were always positive both on an annual and a generational base, except for the period of 2013–2019 (Table 2): F_{PED} of 0.10%/yr, 0.08%/yr, and $-0.12\%/yr$, and ΔF_{PED} of 0.61%, 0.46%, and -0.67% , for the 1975–2000, 2000–2013, and 2013–2019 periods, respectively. After the introduction of GS, rates of pedigree-based inbreeding were again positive: F_{PED} of 0.09%/yr and ΔF_{PED} of 0.51% for the 2019–2021 period. For NRC, F_{PED} increased from 1975 until the introduction of GS in 2016 (Figure 6). Before the introduction of GS, annual rates of F_{PED} ranged between 0.04%/yr and 0.06%/yr (Table 2). Similarly, ΔF_{PED} increased from 0.24% for the 1975–2000 period to 0.26% for the 2010–2016 period, with a smaller F_{PED} for the 2000–2010 period (ΔF_{PED} of 0.16%; Table 2). After the introduction of GS, F_{PED} kept increasing (Figure 6), although with a

Figure 5. Contribution (percentage) of the top 10 sires for animals born in each year. Vertical blue lines indicate the year of onset of genomic selection.

much lower rate: 0.02%/yr for the 2016–2020 period, with a corresponding ΔF_{PED} of 0.05% (Table 2). For ABO, F_{PED} increased steadily for the whole 2000–2020 period (Figure 6). Before the implementation of GS, the annual rate of F_{PED} was 0.18%/yr for the 2000–2014 period, with a corresponding ΔF_{PED} of 1.19%. After the introduction of GS, F_{PED} kept increasing, although with a lower generational rate due the shorter generation interval: the annual rate of F_{PED} was 0.17%/yr, and ΔF_{PED} was 0.99% for the 2014–2020 period (Table 2). For TAR, F_{PED} was rather stable until 2008, then increased over time, including after the introduction of GS (Figure 6). Both annual and generational rates of pedigree-based inbreeding increased after the introduction of GS (Table 2): ΔF_{PED} was 0.35% in 2000–2014 and 0.93% in 2014–2020 (Table 2). Vosgienne had the lowest level of F_{PED} among all French breeds but increased steadily over time (Figure 6). However, after the introduction of GS, both annual and generational rates of F_{PED} decreased, with ΔF_{PED} moving from 0.53% for the 2000–2014 period to 0.23% for the 2014–2020 period (Table 2). Thus, following the introduction of GS, ΔF_{PED} increased in some breeds

(MRY and TAR), whereas it decreased in others (NRC, VOS, and slightly for ABO).

Overall, trends and rates of kinship for all animals in the pedigree followed those of pedigree-based inbreeding, particularly in relation to changes before and after the implementation of GS. For MRY, kinship levels (f_{PED}) were smaller than F_{PED} until 2007, showing avoidance of inbreeding mating. Levels of f_{PED} were then approximately equal to those of F_{PED} up to 2013, and larger for the period 2013–2021 (Figure 6). Kinships differed clearly between sires and dams after 1980 (Figure 6), with kinship between sires being considerably smaller than both kinships between dams and F_{PED} (Figure 6), which indicates that selected sires were recruited from animals less related than the population average. Overall, for MRY, generational rates of kinship (Δf_{PED}) were similar to ΔF_{PED} , being negative before the implementation of GS (−0.45%) for the 2013–2019 period and positive afterward (0.42%) for the 2019–2021 period, although with a smaller rate than before 2013 (0.73%; Table 2). For NRC, f_{PED} was slightly higher than F_{PED} , but overall followed a similar trend (Figure 6). Kinships

Table 2. Average generation interval for both parents (L) in different periods (years interval) for all animals in pedigree (all) and for genotyped animals only (genotyped), along with annual and generational (indicated by Δ) rates of pedigree-based kinship (f_{PED}), inbreeding (F_{PED}) for all animals in the pedigree and of genomic-based inbreeding from ROH (F_{ROH}) or GRM (F_{GRM}) for genotyped animals only, and effective population size (N_e)

Breed	Years interval	L		Annual rate, %				Generational rate (Δ), %				N_e^1		
		All	Genotyped	f_{PED}	F_{PED}	F_{ROH}	F_{GRM}	Δf_{PED}	ΔF_{PED}	ΔF_{ROH}	ΔF_{GRM}	F_{PED}	F_{ROH}	F_{GRM}
MRY	1975–2000	5.84	6.85	0.10	0.10	0.11	0.26	0.61	0.61	0.76	1.77	82	66	28
	2000–2013	5.61	6.21	0.13	0.08	0.08	0.18	0.73	0.46	0.47	1.13	109	106	44
	2013–2019	5.64	5.28	-0.08	-0.12	-0.21	-0.48	-0.45	-0.67	-1.12	-2.54	ND	ND	ND
	2019–2021	5.81	5.40	0.07	0.09	0.17	0.30	0.42	0.51	0.93	1.61	98	54	31
NRC	1975–2000	4.60	4.79	0.05	0.05	0.02	0.07	0.22	0.24	0.09	0.34	208	540	147
	2000–2010	4.52	4.65	0.04	0.04	0.04	-0.04	0.20	0.16	0.18	-0.19	313	278	ND
	2010–2016	4.51	4.55	0.06	0.06	0.02	0.06	0.29	0.26	0.10	0.30	192	478	169
	2016–2022	3.48	3.37	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.11	0.06	0.05	0.06	0.38	1,000	779	133
ABO	2000–2014 ²	6.67	6.59	0.17	0.18	0.36	0.48	1.13	1.19	2.39	3.14	42	21	16
	2014–2020	5.89	5.87	0.10	0.17	0.10	0.17	0.58	0.99	0.58	0.99	51	86	50
TAR	2000–2014 ²	6.55	6.43	0.06	0.05	0.11	0.04	0.38	0.35	0.68	0.28	143	74	179
	2014–2020	5.37	5.39	0.11	0.17	0.16	0.31	0.56	0.93	0.86	1.65	54	58	30
VOS	2000–2014 ²	7.12	6.98	0.06	0.07	0.13	0.20	0.42	0.53	0.88	1.41	94	57	35
	2014–2020	7.77	7.61	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.05	0.10	0.23	0.19	0.40	217	262	126

¹ND = N_e not defined.

²Genomic-based measures were calculated using genomic data in the interval 2012–2014.

Figure 6. Yearly average of pedigree-based coefficients of inbreeding (F_{ped}) and kinship for all animals in the pedigree (f_{ped}), for calves later selected as sires ($f_{sires\ calves}$) and for calves later selected as dams ($f_{dams\ calves}$). Vertical blue lines indicate the year of onset of genomic selection. Kinship measures for dams and sires in years 2020–2021 and 2021 were removed for MRY and French breeds, respectively, as no parents were yet available in these years.

Table 3. Individual average (SE) total genome length in ROH, ROH length, total number of ROH, and number of ROH per length class

Item	MRY	NRC	ABO	TAR	VOS
Total genome length in ROH, Mb	190.54 (0.73)	187.69 (0.09)	203.36 (0.45)	190.00 (0.50)	147.79 (0.86)
ROH length, Mb	1.70 (0.00)	1.82 (0.00)	2.08 (0.00)	1.98 (0.00)	2.09 (0.00)
Total number ROH	111.25 (0.37)	102.38 (0.04)	97.43 (0.18)	95.59 (0.22)	70.08 (0.35)
Number ROH [1–2] Mb	86.44 (0.27)	73.91 (0.03)	62.07 (0.11)	64.17 (0.14)	44.27 (0.20)
Number ROH [2–4] Mb	21.79 (0.12)	23.74 (0.02)	27.18 (0.07)	25.26 (0.09)	19.41 (0.13)
Number ROH [4–8] Mb	3.21 (0.03)	4.60 (0.01)	7.63 (0.03)	5.73 (0.03)	6.00 (0.06)
Number ROH [8–16] Mb	1.02 (0.01)	1.16 (0.00)	1.32 (0.01)	1.24 (0.01)	1.26 (0.02)
Number ROH ≥ 16 Mb	—	—	—	—	—

between dams were clearly higher than those between sires, with f_{PED} for the latter increasing more after 2016. These lower kinships for sires indicate that male calves later becoming sires were selected from animals less related than average. Finally, rates of kinships in NRC were the same (annual rates) or similar (Δf_{PED}) to those of pedigree-based inbreeding (Table 2), with a smaller Δf_{PED} after the introduction of GS. For the French breeds, f_{PED} followed overall the same trend as for F_{PED} (Figure 6). In ABO, f_{PED} was the same or slightly higher than F_{PED} until 2010, to then become slightly lower after the implementation of GS. In TAR, f_{PED} was always higher than F_{PED} , whereas in VOS it was the opposite (Figure 6). In all 3 French breeds, kinships between sires and dams were clearly higher than f_{PED} of all animals, indicating that parents were recruited from animals that were more related than the population average. Finally, after the implementation of GS, Δf_{PED} increased slightly for TAR, whereas it decreased for ABO and VOS (Table 2). Thus, after the introduction of GS, Δf_{PED} increased for MRY and TAR, whereas it decreased for NRC, ABO, and VOS.

ROH-Based Inbreeding Across breeds, the total genome length being in ROH ranged from 147.79 Mb in VOS to 203.36 Mb in ABO (Table 3). The mean ROH length ranged from 1.70 Mb in MRY to 2.09 Mb in VOS, whereas the average number of ROH ranged from 111.25 in MRY to 70.08 in VOS. As expected, shorter ROH were the most represented, and the longest ROH were least represented. Runs of homozygosity of length ≥ 16 Mb were absent in all breeds.

Overall, F_{ROH} inbreeding rates followed a similar pattern as pedigree-based ones. For MRY, F_{ROH} increased steadily from 0.054 in 1975 up to 0.083 in 1998, remaining stable at ~ 0.08 until 2013 (Figure 7). Similar to F_{PED} , F_{ROH} showed a decreasing trend for the 2013–2019 period (F_{ROH} of 0.069 in 2019), and a slight increase from 2019 onward (Figure 7). Before GS, the generational rates of ROH-based genomic inbreeding (ΔF_{ROH}) were positive except for the 2013–2019 period, and increased again to similar levels after the introduction of GS (ΔF_{ROH} of -1.12% and 0.93% in the 2013–2019 and 2019–2021 periods, respectively; Table 2). For NRC, F_{ROH} was overall

stable across years (Figure 7). Annual and generational rates of ROH-based genomic inbreeding in NRC were overall smaller than pedigree-based ones (Table 2) and decreased in the period before the introduction of GS: ΔF_{ROH} of 0.18, 0.10, and 0.06 for the 2000–2010, 2010–2016, and 2016–2022 periods, respectively (Table 2). For the French breeds, only 3 years of genomic data were available for the period before the implementation of GS. For ABO, ΔF_{ROH} was much higher than ΔF_{PED} : 2.39% for the 2012–2014 period and then decreasing after the introduction of GS (0.58% in 2014–2020; Table 2). In TAR, ΔF_{ROH} increased after the introduction of GS from 0.68% for the 2012–2014 period to 0.86% for the 2014–2020 period (Table 2). For VOS, ΔF_{ROH} decreased after the introduction of GS from 0.88% for the 2012–2014 period to 0.19% for the 2014–2020 period (Table 2). Thus, after the implementation of GS, ΔF_{ROH} increased for MRY and TAR but decreased in NRC, ABO, and VOS.

Changes in ROH segments of different length (Figure 8 and Figure 9) generally aligned with the trend in F_{PED} (Figure 6) For MRY, the total genome length being in ROH decreased after GS, with this decrease being mostly due to a reduction in shorter ROH segments (between 1 and 4 Mb), whereas longer ones slightly increased (Figure 9). For NRC, ABO, and TAR, the total genome length being in ROH increased after GS, with these increases being mostly due to an increment in short and medium ROH segments. For VOS, the total genome length in ROH remained more or less stable after GS.

When comparing trends in F_{ROH_k} , the largest changes were observed for short and medium ROH segments (between 1 and 2 and 2–4 Mb), whereas longer ROH segments remained more stable over time (Figure 8). Furthermore, ΔF_{ROH_k} for short and medium ROH segments were overall larger compared with longer ROH segments (Table 4). For example, for MRY, F_{ROH_k} clearly decreased before the implementation of GS for the shorter segments (Figure 8), with a ΔF_{ROH_k} of -0.66 (ROH of 1–2 Mb) and -0.36 (2–4 Mb), whereas for the longer segments, the decrease was small ($\Delta F_{ROH_k} = -0.04$ for 4–8 Mb) or absent (8–16 Mb; Table 4). After the implementation of GS, the F_{ROH_k} increases were stronger for the short seg-

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Figure 7. Trends of genomic inbreeding based on ROH (F_{ROH} ; in red, left panels) and on the genomic relationship matrix (F_{GRM} ; in green, right panels) for genotyped animals. Vertical blue lines indicate the year of onset of genomic selection. Note that the y-axis scale for F_{ROH} and F_{GRM} is different.

Figure 8. F_{ROH} trends of ROH at different length class. Vertical blue lines indicate the year of onset of genomic selection. Missing values indicate that no ROH was present in that class. Error bars represent SE. Note that the y-axis scale is different depending on the breed.

ments (ΔF_{ROH_k} of 0.20 for 1–2 Mb and 0.57 for 2–4 Mb) than for the longer segments (0.05 for 4–8 Mb and 8–16 Mb). In the French breeds, F_{ROH_k} clearly increased over all years analyzed for the shorter segments, but not as much as for the longer segments (Figure 8). In all breeds, the longer segments covered just a small part of the total genome length of all ROH (Figure 9). The smaller segments in the MRY covered larger parts of the genome (>100 Mb) in comparison to the other breeds (<100 Mb), whereas the longer segments covered less than 9.5 Mb in the MRY after GS and between 10.2 and 12.5 Mb in the other breeds.

GRM-Based Inbreeding Overall, trends of F_{GRM} closely followed those of F_{ROH} , with a difference in scale in the overall level of inbreeding (Figure 7). The GRM-based rates of inbreeding per generation (ΔF_{GRM}) showed a higher magnitude compared with ΔF_{ROH} , with ΔF_{GRM} being over 1% in at least one of the periods analyzed for all breeds except NRC (Table 2). For all breeds and periods, changes for ΔF_{GRM} were consistent with changes for ΔF_{ROH} , with the exception of NRC. For NRC, changes in ΔF_{GRM} were opposite to ΔF_{ROH} ones: ΔF_{GRM} decreased between 1975 and 2000 and 2000–2010, and increased afterward, including after the implementation of GS. After the implementation of GS, ΔF_{GRM} increased for MRY, NRC, and TAR, but decreased in ABO and VOS. Finally, for MRY and ABO, ΔF_{GRM} was close to or higher than 1% after the implementation of GS.

Comparison of Inbreeding Coefficients Inbreeding coefficients F_{ROH} , F_{GRM} , and F_{PED} were compared by computing the Pearson correlation between each pair of inbreeding coefficients for all genotyped animals in the years analyzed (Table 1). Overall, F_{ROH} was highly correlated with F_{GRM} for all breeds, with correlations ranging from 0.92 for NRC and TAR to 0.95 for MRY (Table 5). Correlations between F_{ROH} and F_{PED} and between F_{GRM} and F_{PED} were lower for the French breeds compared with MRY and NRC. Correlations between F_{ROH} and F_{PED} ranged from 0.30 for TAR to 0.58 for MRY. Correlations between F_{GRM} and F_{PED} ranged from 0.31 for TAR to 0.53 for MRY, and were overall lower than correlations between F_{ROH} and F_{PED} (Table 5). Furthermore, the correlations between F_{ROH} , F_{GRM} , and F_{PED} changed over time (Table 6). Overall, both the correlation between F_{ROH} and F_{PED} and the correlation between F_{GRM} and F_{PED} decreased over time for all breeds, except for NRC. Across breeds, the correlation between F_{ROH} and F_{GRM} showed no clear trend over time. Moreover, correlations between F_{ROH} , F_{GRM} , and F_{PED} with F_{ROH_k} from ROH of different length classes were generally the lowest for the longest ROH class (8–16 Mb; Table 7). For MRY, F_{ROH} , F_{GRM} , and F_{PED} all showed the highest correlations with short ROH of length 1 to 2 Mb. For all other breeds, F_{ROH} , F_{GRM} , and F_{PED} showed the highest correlations with ROH of length 2 to 4 Mb (Table 5). Overall, for all

Figure 9. Average genome coverage (in Mb) per ROH class for year intervals considered. Gray areas indicate the interval after the onset of genomic selection. Error bars represent SE.

breeds, stronger correlations were observed with F_{ROH} , followed by F_{GRM} , and F_{PED} .

DISCUSSION

Genomic selection has had a profound influence on dairy cattle breeding, leading to changes in the structure

Table 4. Annual and generational rates (indicated by Δ) of ROH genomic inbreeding (F_{ROH}) and of F_{ROH} using ROH within specific lengths

Breed	Years interval	F_{ROH}	Annual inbreeding rate, %					Generational inbreeding rate (ΔF), %			
			F_{ROH} [1–2] Mb	F_{ROH} [2–4] Mb	F_{ROH} [4–8] Mb	F_{ROH} [8–16] Mb	ΔF_{ROH}	ΔF_{ROH} [1–2] Mb	ΔF_{ROH} [2–4] Mb	ΔF_{ROH} [4–8] Mb	ΔF_{ROH} [8–16] Mb
MRY	1975–2000	0.11	0.06	0.04	0.00	NA ¹	0.76	0.43	0.26	0.01	—
	2000–2013	0.08	0.05	0.03	0.00	NA ¹	0.47	0.31	0.16	0.00	—
	2013–2019	–0.21	–0.12	–0.07	–0.01	0.00	–1.12	–0.66	–0.36	–0.04	0.00
	2019–2021	0.17	0.04	0.11	0.01	0.01	0.93	0.20	0.57	0.05	0.05
NRD	1975–2000	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.09	0.04	0.04	0.01	0.01
	2000–2010	0.04	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.18	0.05	0.09	0.00	0.01
	2010–2016	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.06	0.03	–0.01	0.01
	2016–2022	0.02	0.02	0.00	–0.01	0.00	0.06	0.07	0.02	–0.02	–0.01
ABO	2000–2014 ²	0.36	0.08	0.15	0.10	0.02	2.39	0.56	0.97	0.65	0.14
	2014–2020	0.10	0.03	0.05	0.02	0.00	0.58	0.17	0.27	0.11	–0.02
TAR	2000–2014 ²	0.11	0.06	0.00	0.06	–0.02	0.68	0.40	0.00	0.39	–0.16
	2014–2020	0.16	0.05	0.07	0.02	0.00	0.86	0.25	0.39	0.13	0.02
VOS	2000–2014 ²	0.13	0.05	0.03	0.03	0.00	0.88	0.33	0.22	0.21	0.02
	2014–2020	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.19	0.05	0.15	–0.03	0.01

¹NA are due to missing averages for ROH segments of length 8–16 Mb.

²Genomic-based measures were calculated using genomic data in the interval 2012–2014.

of breeding programs (Schaeffer, 2006; Van Eenennaam et al., 2014), decreased generation intervals (Schaeffer, 2006), and increased rates of improvement for TMI (e.g., García-Ruiz et al., 2016; Doublet et al., 2019), but also variable changes in genetic diversity among breeds (see Introduction). Therefore, it is important to evaluate and monitor the possible impact of GS on genetic diversity, especially for local cattle breeds. The increasing availability of genomic data offers opportunity to gain additional insights into the genetic diversity of local cattle breeds. In this study, we investigated changes in genetic diversity and population demographic structure in 5 local European cattle breeds from 3 countries. Hereafter, we first discuss the results of the observed changes in genetic diversity in relation to the breeds' population size and due to the implementation of GS in the 5 breeds. Next, we discuss the impact of management factors on the breeds' genetic diversity and their population demographic structure. We then discuss the impact of different inbreeding metrics. Finally, we discuss the implications of this study.

Table 5. Correlations between F_{ROH} , F_{GRM} , and F_{PED}

Breed	F_{ROH}, F_{GRM}	F_{ROH}, F_{PED}	F_{GRM}, F_{PED}
MRY	0.95	0.58	0.53
NRC	0.92	0.55	0.48
ABO	0.94	0.37	0.38
TAR	0.92	0.30	0.31
VOS	0.94	0.47	0.46

Genetic Diversity and Population Size Within Breeds

The 5 breeds analyzed in this study vary in population size, with NRC being the largest. The population of the NRC breed is more than 4 to 8 times greater than the second largest breed (ABO), depending on the metric used (i.e., self-reported numbers in the Domestic Animal Diversity Information System; FAO, 2025; Table 1; or the total registered number of male or female calves in the pedigree) regardless of whether they later become parents (Supplemental Figure S3). On the other hand, the VOS and MRV breeds are 4 to 8 times smaller in population than ABO. These differences in population size did not translate directly into differences in inbreeding level, rates, and realized effective population sizes (Table 2). Although the largest breed (NRC) had generally low inbreeding rates and large effective population sizes, the highest inbreeding rates per generation and smallest

Table 6. Correlations between F_{ROH} , F_{GRM} , and F_{PED} in different time intervals

Breed	Years interval	F_{ROH}, F_{GRM}	F_{ROH}, F_{PED}	F_{GRM}, F_{PED}
MRY	1975–2000	0.94	0.72	0.66
MRY	2000–2013	0.96	0.58	0.51
MRY	2013–2019	0.95	0.54	0.50
MRY	2019–2021	0.91	0.59	0.49
NRC	1975–2000	0.90	0.53	0.43
NRC	2000–2010	0.90	0.57	0.45
NRC	2010–2016	0.92	0.54	0.48
NRC	2016–2022	0.92	0.54	0.49
ABO	2012–2014	0.93	0.44	0.47
ABO	2014–2020	0.94	0.37	0.37
TAR	2012–2014	0.91	0.34	0.36
TAR	2014–2020	0.92	0.29	0.31
VOS	2012–2014	0.95	0.55	0.52
VOS	2014–2020	0.94	0.45	0.45

Table 7. Pearson correlations between F_{ROH} , F_{GRM} , or F_{PED} with F_{ROH_k} inbreeding for ROH at different length

Breed	[1–2] Mb	[2–4] Mb	[4–8] Mb	[8–16] Mb
MRY				
F_{ROH}	0.91	0.88	0.60	0.19
F_{GRM}	0.90	0.81	0.52	0.17
F_{PED}	0.47	0.57	0.36	0.16
NRC				
F_{ROH}	0.78	0.87	0.69	0.28
F_{GRM}	0.72	0.80	0.63	0.26
F_{PED}	0.37	0.49	0.40	0.23
ABO				
F_{ROH}	0.81	0.86	0.76	0.28
F_{GRM}	0.78	0.82	0.69	0.27
F_{PED}	0.32	0.32	0.27	0.09
TAR				
F_{ROH}	0.77	0.82	0.67	0.24
F_{GRM}	0.72	0.76	0.61	0.23
F_{PED}	0.24	0.24	0.20	0.06
VOS				
F_{ROH}	0.84	0.89	0.81	0.37
F_{GRM}	0.81	0.84	0.73	0.34
F_{PED}	0.40	0.42	0.36	0.18

effective population sizes were found for the second largest breed (ABO) before the implementation of GS (Table 2). Moreover, inbreeding rates per generation varied within breeds from one period to the other. For example, in MRY inbreeding rates per generation were negative between 2013 and 2019 but relatively large (>0.40%) in all other periods. Finally, for all breeds except NRC, inbreeding rates per generation above 0.5% and effective population sizes below 100 occurred. Thus, genetic management is needed to avoid having effective population sizes fall below 50, a value below which populations are considered at risk of extinction (FAO, 2000). Our results obtained from pedigree- and genomic-based estimates of N_e also underscore the importance of using pedigree- or genomic-based estimates of effective population size for genetic management rather than census size alone or N_e measures derived from it (FAO, 2000; Rochus et al., 2025). Moreover, genetic management is also needed to avoid skewed sires' contributions in the population, which is an important factor in reducing genetic diversity and effective population sizes (Howard et al., 2017).

Changes in Genetic Diversity After the Implementation of GS

Overall, the observed changes in genetic diversity due to the implementation of GS for the 5 breeds analyzed align with those reported in other studies (e.g., Doekes et al., 2018; Doublet et al., 2019; Lozada-Soto et al., 2021). With the implementation of GS, we observed that generation intervals for sires decreased (except for MRY; Figure 4), and changes in generational rates of inbreed-

ing (ΔF) and kinship (Δf_{PED}) varied (Table 2 and Figure 4). For MRY, only 2 years of data were available after the implementation of GS; therefore, strong conclusions should be avoided. Nonetheless, for MRY, Δf_{PED} , ΔF_{PED} , ΔF_{ROH} , and ΔF_{GRM} all increased after the introduction of GS in 2019 compared with the rate for the 2013–2019 period, although both Δf_{PED} and ΔF_{ROH} rates were smaller than those before 2013. For NRC, Δf_{PED} , ΔF_{PED} , and ΔF_{ROH} all decreased after the introduction of GS, whereas ΔF_{GRM} increased. Finally, after the introduction of GS, Δf_{PED} , ΔF_{PED} , ΔF_{ROH} , and ΔF_{GRM} all decreased for ABO and VOS, whereas they all increased for TAR. Therefore, changes in genetic diversity after the introduction of GS were not consistent across breeds, with the timing of these changes not always corresponding to the introduction of GS. Thus, other genetic management factors are likely influencing inbreeding and kinship rates in these breeds beyond just the introduction of GS per se.

It is not fully clear why inbreeding rates per generation (ΔF) increased after the introduction of GS in cosmopolitan dairy cattle breeds, but not in some other breeds (Doekes, 2020). One possible reason is that although more bulls are screened for selection with the availability of genomic information, fewer bulls are marketed, leading to a higher contribution of the selected bulls to the next generation. A lack of genomic control of inbreeding (Sonesson et al., 2012) and the strategy to update the reference population (Eynard et al., 2018a) may also play a role on the estimation of genomic-based inbreeding and on the impact on genetic diversity, respectively. Eynard et al. (2018a) showed that the method used to update the reference population, particularly the relatedness among individuals, could affect the breeding population and slightly affect the genetic diversity in the long term, both in terms of inbreeding and of heterozygosity. Finally, intense competition between AI companies to provide bulls for the market with high breeding values for TMI may have shifted the focus to short-term gains, rather than increasing genetic diversity needed for long-term gain, especially in major cosmopolitan cattle breeds (Doekes et al., 2018; Eynard et al., 2018b; Doublet et al., 2019; Doekes, 2020). In this study, we showed that changes in ΔF were variable and that increases in ΔF following the introduction of GS are not limited to the major cosmopolitan cattle breeds, as ΔF also increased in TAR and MRY, both of which have relatively small population sizes.

Overall, changes in F_{PED} , F_{ROH} , and F_{GRM} trends were in agreement, with increments and decrements occurring in the same period, despite correlations between pedigree-based F_{PED} and genomic-based inbreeding measures (F_{ROH} and F_{GRM}) ranging between 0.30 and 0.58 (Table 5). Differences in ΔF tended to be stronger when based

on ROH or GRM. For example, in ABO, ΔF_{PED} changed from 1.19% to 0.99%, whereas ΔF_{ROH} changed from 2.76% to 0.68%. Runs of homozygosity allow capturing inbreeding arising from ancestors in more remote generations (Keller et al., 2011; Speed and Balding, 2015). In this study, we used ROH with a minimum length of 1,000 kb; a rough estimate of the average number of generations captured by such ROH length is ~ 50 generations (Doekes et al., 2018). Consequently, in this study, F_{ROH} captured inbreeding due to ancestors long before the start of the pedigrees, explaining why F_{ROH} levels were overall higher than F_{PED} ones, especially for MRY and NRC at the start in the 1970s. Moreover, lack of deep pedigree information may lead to underestimate the level of F_{PED} , but it does not affect F_{ROH} or F_{GRM} estimates. Overall, the average number of CGE (Doekes et al., 2018) across years was higher for NRC and MRY compared with French breeds (Supplemental Figure S2). Nonetheless, the level of F_{PED} was lower than that of F_{ROH} and of F_{GRM} for all breeds analyzed, possibly reflecting that genomic-based measures such as ROH and marker-based homozygosity capture more ancient inbreeding than pedigree does. Finally, another reason why ΔF_{ROH} and ΔF_{PED} may differ is because genotyped animals may not be a random sample of animals in the pedigree. We checked for MRY whether the F_{PED} of genotyped animals differed from the population average and found that F_{PED} tended to be slightly higher for genotyped animals, especially in the last decade (results not shown). On the other hand, in VOS, all animals are genotyped, and estimated levels of F_{ROH} were still higher than F_{PED} . Thus, these results suggest a limited impact of selective genotyping and that the observed differences between ΔF_{ROH} or ΔF_{GRM} and ΔF_{PED} may be due to genomic-based measurements capturing more ancient inbreeding than pedigree-based measurements.

Inbreeding estimated by ROH of different lengths ($F_{ROH,k}$) showed different patterns of change over time (Figure 8). The F_{ROH} measured with shorter segments not only had a higher level, but changes were larger as well. This pattern can be clearly seen in the French breeds, where after the introduction of GS, F_{ROH} clearly increased for shorter segments (1–2 Mb and 2–4 Mb) but stayed mostly constant for longer segments (8–16 Mb). Moreover, after GS, rates of inbreeding per generation for the French breeds were larger ($\Delta F_{ROH,k}$ up to 0.39%) for the shortest ROH segments than for the longest segments (Table 4). These results may suggest that increases in inbreeding after the introduction of GS are primarily due to inbreeding caused by more ancient ancestors. This pattern is in agreement with simulation results of Forutan et al. (2018), which showed an higher frequency of short and intermediate ROH segments after GS compared with pedigree-based selection. The increased frequency

of shorter segments under GS could be explained by its ability to select for or against variants originating from ancient ancestors not recorded in the pedigree (Doekes et al., 2018; Forutan et al., 2018).

Inbreeding originating from ancient common ancestors tends to be less harmful than inbreeding due to recent common ancestors (Doekes et al., 2019). In this study, we observed larger changes of short ROH after the introduction of GS (Figure 8, Tables 3 and 4). Although shorter ROH are associated with ancient inbreeding, changes in F_{ROH} cannot be compared directly with changes in F_{GRM} or homozygosity. Indeed, F_{ROH} is not cumulative as inbreeding theory expects F to be. Although inbreeding and homozygosity always increase in a closed population of finite size, under random mating, F_{ROH} will, at the same time, decrease because ROH segments break down due to recombination. Consequently, in a large expanding population with a ΔF of approximately 0, ΔF_{ROH} will be negative. This explains why ΔF_{ROH} based on long segments (>4 Mb) is lower than ΔF_{ROH} based on short segments, both before (see, for instance, MRY in the 1975–2000 period; Table 4) and after the introduction of GS. Finally, this expected impact of recombination on ROH segments but not on homozygosity captured in F_{GRM} may also explain the differences observed between changes in ΔF_{ROH} and ΔF_{GRM} .

Impact of Management Factors and Changes in Population Demographic Structure

In the MRY, several changes in demographic population structure and breeding occurred along with the introduction of GS. The first change is a shift from predominantly natural matings on farm by local bulls to AI by bulls from the national breeding program. This shift largely explains the reduction in the number of male calves born per year that later become sires and the number of sires used, beginning as early as 1975 (Figures 2 and 3). The second change is the use in the breeding nucleus of management strategies such as ensuring that progeny-tested bulls originate from different parents, and the cold sire system (Hiemstra and de Haas, 2004) from around 2000 onward. In this system, $\sim 20,000$ semen doses from each of 10 bulls are cryopreserved each year. In this way, after the bulls have been progeny tested, there is a large variety of bulls available for artificial insemination. Thus, such system enables the use of less related bulls as sires, thereby reducing the inbreeding rates in the main population. Initially, the effect of such strategies is only seen in the reduced kinship of the calves that later have been selected as a breeding bull (Figure 6). Because the generation interval was above 6 years at that time and cows were generally selected on farm, it took until 2013 before the effect of these strategies in the central nucleus was

seen at the population level, after which both the average population kinship and inbreeding levels declined (Figure 6). Our results overall agree with those reported by Hiemstra and de Haas (2004), who performed a pedigree-based analysis including data up to 2004. Although only 3 years of data were available since the onset of GS in 2018, estimated kinships and inbreeding levels in MRY are on the rise again. Although the number of sires used is about the same as before GS, the skewness of sires' contributions shows an increasing trend in the last 3 years (Figures 3 and 5). This pattern suggests a possible increasing trend in inbreeding due to a more one-sided use of bulls available through GS. Finally, we observed higher levels of kinship for calves later becoming dams compared with calves later becoming sires (kinships levels started to diverge from the 1980–1990 period onward), indicating that, on average, selected dams are more related than selected sires. These results highlight the possibility to reduce kinship and possible loss of genetic diversity by implementing additional management strategies on the dams' side.

In NRC, OCS was implemented in 2010. Kinships at the population level continued increasing with a slightly higher rate following the introduction of OCS, but declined after the introduction of GS. Moreover, the number of bulls used as sires (Figure 3) increased around 2000 and from 2010 onward, with the latter being due to a more complete recording of natural matings. There was no obvious explanation for the peak in recordings of natural matings around the year 2000. Finally, it is clear that since 2017, fewer bulls are selected as sires per year, these bulls are younger, and their contribution is more even (Figures 1, 2, 4, and 5). Thus, these results suggest that the introduction of OCS in NRC has mitigated the reduction in number of used bulls after the introduction of GS. Nonetheless, despite the increased number of calves selected as sires and dams in recent years, the kinship of selected sires also increased, especially after 2017. Such observed increases in kinship may lead to an increase in inbreeding levels in future generations.

For the French breeds, the number of bulls used as sires per year increased from around 2008 onward, thus before the introduction of GS (Figure 3). Moreover, the reduction in the sires' generation interval after the introduction of GS corresponded with more equal contributions of bulls, although both of these took longer in VOS compared with other French breeds (Figure 5 and Figure 4). A likely reason for these observed trends, such as the more balanced sire contributions, is related to management practices, as specific recommendations were provided to breeding companies before the implementation of GS, aiming to optimize both genetic gain and the preservation of genetic diversity (see Colleau et al., 2015). In particular, at a given constant cost, GS allows more

bulls to be proposed to the market than under progeny testing. Moreover, all these 3 French breeds have an active management of their genetic diversity, as they are very local, with only one or 2 companies in charge of the breeding scheme. Such companies aim to preserve the genetic potential of their breeds because no rescue would be possible from other sources (Doublet et al., 2019). Therefore, this management relies on the use of so-called “originality indices,” such as “ORIX” and “ISUO,” which enhance a bull's estimated breeding value based on its genetic distance with the current reproductive population. Additionally, the lowest level of inbreeding (pedigree and genomic) observed for VOS could possibly be due to the less intense selection pressure for production traits (such as milk) in this breed compared with the other French breeds analyzed. Finally, for the ABO breed, lost families were reintroduced in the early 2000s in the breeding scheme by using cryopreserved semen of old bulls (born ~30 years earlier; Jacques et al., 2023). This intervention has led to an increase in genetic diversity and variance, as well as improved performance for certain traits that had declined over time, such as reproduction traits (Jacques et al., 2023). This genetic management strategy is partially reflected in the f_{PED} trend (Figure 6), which shows a higher rate of kinship at the population level in the early 2000s, followed by a reduced rate thereafter. Moreover, the impact of this intervention may be reflected in the increased generation intervals for sires during the same period, as reintroduced bulls could have been used first as active breeding sires in the 1990s and later as cryopreserved sires between 2004 and 2010, thereby increasing their generation intervals relative to other contemporary sires. Finally, the effect of this intervention may appear with some delay relative to the reintroduction of lost families, likely due to the time needed for the strategy to take effect.

In all breeds, the contributions of the top sires reduced and got more even after the introduction of GS (Figure 5). Only for VOS this pattern may be (partly) explained by the higher number of sires used after the introduction of GS, whereas for the other breeds the number of bulls used as sires per year remained similar or even decreased (Figure 3). For NRC, the contributions of the top sires may have become more even because of the introduction of OCS. Nonetheless, it is interesting to notice that a more even contribution of the top sires was observed after the introduction of GS in all 5 breeds. Whether this pattern reflects the direct effects of using GS or a growing awareness on the importance of managing relatedness and inbreeding remains unclear. A possible explanation may be that GS enables a higher turnover among the top sires, with young bulls entering the top rankings more frequently compared with progeny testing, in which bulls often remained in the top 10 for many

years, leading to disproportionately large contributions, especially in small breeds. Another possible explanation could be that GS allows for a more accurate evaluation of a larger number of bulls than progeny testing, which may result in selecting sires with more similar estimated breeding values that are consequently used more evenly in the population. Nonetheless, even with a more balanced contribution of sires, population inbreeding may still increase if the selected sires are closely related.

Impact of Inbreeding Metrics

We have measured inbreeding and inbreeding rates with different metrics: F_{PED} , F_{GRM} , F_{ROH} , and F_{ROH} with ROH segments of different length classes. In general, the trends observed within breeds with these different metrics were similar. The general conclusion that changes in inbreeding after the introduction of GS were not consistent over breeds did not depend on the metric used. We further evaluated whether inbreeding analyzed by the decay of linkage disequilibrium (LD) showed the same pattern observed with other genomic-based inbreeding metrics (Supplemental Figure S4, see Notes). Overall, the LD decay showed a similar pattern to that of F_{ROH} (Figures 8 and 9), although differences between breeds and periods were not as clear as with F_{ROH} . Overall, LD decreased after GS in MRY, whereas it increased in NRC, ABO, and TAR and remained stable for VOS (Supplemental Figure S4). This pattern was consistent with the changes observed after the implementation of GS for the total length of the genome being in ROH (Figure 9).

Correlations between the different metrics were below unity, especially those between genomic measures (F_{ROH} or F_{GRM}) and pedigree-based inbreeding (correlation ranging between 0.30 and 0.58, Table 5). Overall, these correlations align with those reported in other studies. Our results align with those observed by Doublet et al. (2019), who reported correlations between F_{PED} and F_{ROH} ranging from 0.50 to 0.59 for 3 French dairy cattle breeds (Holstein, Montbéliarde, and Normande). In Dutch Holstein-Friesian, Doekes et al. (2019) reported correlations between F_{PED} and F_{ROH} or F_{GRM} of 0.66 and 0.61, respectively, whereas in American Angus, Lozada-Soto et al. (2021) reported correlations of 0.64 and 0.63, respectively. Finally, in Alpine Grey, a local cattle breed, Gomez Proto et al. (2024) reported a correlation between F_{PED} and F_{ROH} of 0.51. On the other hand, correlations between F_{ROH} and F_{GRM} in our study were high and positive, ranging from 0.92 to 0.95 (Table 5), similar to those observed in other studies (Pryce et al., 2014; Doekes et al., 2019; Lozada-Soto et al., 2021). The F_{PED} can differ from genomic-based inbreeding because of errors in the pedigree, limited pedigree depth, and the inability to distinguish differences caused by Mendelian sampling

within families. Moreover, the observed decrease over time of the correlations between pedigree-based and genomic-based measures are likely due to the accumulation of Mendelian sampling over time (Table 6), in agreement with results reported by Doekes et al. (2018). Finally, the smallest correlations between metrics were found between F_{ROH_k} of the longest segments (8–16 Mb) and the other metrics F_{ROH} , F_{PED} , and F_{GRM} (between 0.06 and 0.37 across breeds, Table 6). These low correlations are to be expected because ROH of longer segments only capture a small part of the total inbreeding (i.e., inbreeding due to recent ancestors). Runs of homozygosity of the longer segments covered a smaller part of the genome than what generally reported in literature (e.g., Forutan et al., 2018; Lozada-Soto et al., 2022), with ROH segments equal to or longer than 16 Mb being completely absent in our study. The small number or absence of long ROH segments may be due to avoidance of matings between close relatives due to the genetic management measures taken in all 5 breeds to avoid excessive inbreeding, such as the use of the cold sire system in MRY, or OCS in NRC. In addition, we should mention that the medium density of the genotypes (between 41K and 51K SNP) may also prevent us from detecting very short as well as very long ROH, as the distance between 2 consecutive SNPs could exceed the threshold definition for an ROH.

Implications

High inbreeding rates pose a risk for populations. According to FAO, populations with ΔF above 1% per generation are threatened with extinction, and those with a ΔF above 0.5% are vulnerable (FAO, 2000; Meuwissen and Oldenbroek, 2017). Following these guidelines, all breeds in this study had ΔF_{PED} or ΔF_{ROH} below the 1% limit, although ABO had values above 1% for the 2000–2014 period (both ΔF_{PED} and ΔF_{ROH}). Notably, with the exception of NRC, all breeds are, or have been in the past, above the 0.5% limit for ΔF for both ΔF_{PED} and ΔF_{ROH} . Furthermore, ΔF_{GRM} was above the 1% limit for MRY and TAR, and has been above 1% in the past for all breeds except NRC. Thus, the results of this study underline how all breeds have to monitor inbreeding and kinship levels, as well as highlight the importance of their genetic management. Theoretically, the most efficient genetic management is the use of optimal contributions (Meuwissen, 1997). Indeed, the implementation of population management strategies following OCS-like principles, such as the cold sire system, and ensuring that progeny-tested bulls originate from different parents in MRY, seems to have been effective in lowering kinship levels, and has been accompanied by a delayed reduction in inbreeding at the population level. This delay is expected because genetic management strategies such

as OCS specifically target the average kinship level of animals selected for breeding rather than the kinship of individual bulls and cows being mated. Thus, OCS ensures genetic diversity in the long term, whereas minimizing the kinship of mating pairs works (only) in the short term.

Genomic selection has accelerated cattle breeding through, for example, the reduction of generation intervals, as also observed in this study. Misztal and Lourenco (2024) suggested that the acceleration brought by GS may lead to increased risks for health and animal welfare when the potential negative impacts on such traits are not noticed in time and properly addressed. Our study suggests that decreased genetic diversity is not caused by the introduction of GS per se. Indeed, effects of genetic management measures, such as the introduction of OCS or OCS-like principles such as the cold sire system, may have a positive effect on genetic diversity. Nonetheless, because of the acceleration in breeding due to GS, the adverse effects on genetic diversity can occur more quickly than before the introduction of GS due to management practices that aim to achieve higher genetic gains, such as selecting too few and/or more related bulls, and without proper control of genetic diversity. Consequently, genetic diversity management is all the more important when GS is applied.

CONCLUSIONS

We investigated changes in population demographic structure and genetic diversity due to the introduction of GS in 5 European local cattle breeds. Overall, the implementation of GS led to a reduction in sires' generation intervals. Moreover, we observed a reduction in the number of calves that later became sires and, for the French breeds, an increase in the number of sires used in the population, likely due to GS enabling the preselection of selection candidates in addition to screening for a higher number of young bulls. After the introduction of GS, the contribution of the top 10 sires was more balanced, except for MRY, in which a balanced contribution was already present. Changes in genetic diversity did occur, but were not consistent across breeds. Overall, rates of kinship, pedigree inbreeding, and genomic inbreeding increased in some breeds (MRY and TAR) but decreased in others (NRC, ABO, and VOS). This study suggests that increases in inbreeding rates may occur after the introduction of GS, although they may not be directly due to the introduction of GS per se. The effect of population management strategies, such as the introduction of the cold sire system in MRY or OCS in NRC, may have a much stronger effect in decreasing kinship and inbreeding rates in the longer term. Therefore, after the implementation of GS, it is essential to monitor changes

in both genetic diversity and population demographic structure and adapt the breed management accordingly when necessary.

NOTES

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Nonstandard abbreviations used: ABO = Abundance; AI = artificial insemination; CGE = complete generation equivalent; F_{GRM} = genomic inbreeding coefficient based on the genomic relationship matrix; F_{PED} = pedigree-based inbreeding coefficient; f_{PED} = pedigree-based kinship coefficient; F_{ROH} = genomic inbreeding coefficient based on runs of homozygosity; F_{ROH_k} = inbreeding coefficient for ROK class k ; GRM = genomic relationship matrix; GS = genomic selection; LD = linkage disequilibrium; MRY = Meuse Rhine Yssel; ND = N_e not defined; N_e = effective population size; NRC = Norwegian Red Cattle; NVI = Dutch-Flemish total merit index; OCS = optimum contribution selection; ROH = runs of homozygosity; TAR = Tarentaise; TMI = total merit index; VOS = Vosgienne; ΔF = rate of inbreeding per generation; Δf = rate of kinship per generation.

REFERENCES

- Ablondi, M., A. Sabbioni, G. Stocco, C. Cipolat-Gotet, C. Dadousis, J. T. van Kaam, R. Finocchiaro, and A. Summer. 2022. Genetic diversity in the Italian Holstein dairy cattle based on pedigree and SNP data prior and after genomic selection. *Front. Vet. Sci.* 8:773985. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2021.773985>.
- AgroParisTech. 2025a. Race Bovine Abundance. Accessed. <https://svs.agroparistech.fr/especes/bovins/abondanc.htm>.
- AgroParisTech. 2025b. Race Bovine Vosgienne. Accessed. <https://svs.agroparistech.fr/especes/bovins/vosgien.htm>.
- Biscarini, F., P. Cozzi, G. Gaspa, and G. Marras. 2019. detectRUNS: Detect Runs of Homozygosity and Runs of Heterozygosity in Diploid Genomes. R package version 0.9.6.
- Bonifazi, R., J. ten Napel, and R. Veerkamp. 2022. How genomic selection has made animal breeding even more important for herd health and fertility. Pages 137–142 in 7th national and 3rd international Herd Health and Management Congress. Antalya, Turkey.

- Broman, K. W., and J. L. Weber. 1999. Long homozygous chromosomal segments in reference families from the centre d'Etude du polymorphisme humain. *Am. J. Hum. Genet.* 65:1493–1500. <https://doi.org/10.1086/302661>.
- Browning, S. R. 2008. Estimation of Pairwise Identity by Descent From Dense Genetic Marker Data in a Population Sample of Haplotypes. *Genetics* 178:2123–2132. <https://doi.org/10.1534/genetics.107.084624>.
- Callegaro, S., F. Tiezzi, C. Maltecca, M. C. Fabbri, J. C. Do Carmo Panetto, and R. Bozzi. 2025. Comprehensive analysis of inbreeding depression across growth, fertility, and survival traits in Limousine beef cattle. *Animal* 19:101672. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.animal.2025.101672>.
- Calus, M. P. L., and J. Vandenplas. 2016. Calc_grm—A program to compute pedigree, genomic, and combined relationship matrices. Wageningen UR Livestock Research, Wageningen, the Netherlands.
- Chang, C. C., C. C. Chow, L. C. Tellier, S. Vattikuti, S. M. Purcell, and J. J. Lee. 2015. Second-generation PLINK: Rising to the challenge of larger and richer datasets. *Gigascience* 4:s13742-015-0047-8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13742-015-0047-8>.
- Cole, J. B. 2015. A simple strategy for managing many recessive disorders in a dairy cattle breeding program. *Genet. Sel. Evol.* 47:94. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12711-015-0174-9>.
- Colleau, J., S. Fritz, F. Guillaume, A. Baur, D. Dupassieux, L. Journaux, A. Eggen, and D. Boichard. 2015. Simulation des potentialités de la sélection génomique chez les bovins laitiers. *INRAE Productions Animales* 28:251–258. <https://doi.org/10.20870/productions-animales.2015.28.3.3030>.
- CRV. 2018a. GENOOSTESTEN BIJ MRIJ EEN FEIT. Accessed Nov. 14, 2022. <https://www.cooperatie-crv.nl/aeu-blog/genoostesten-bij-mrij/>.
- CRV. 2018b. E-Chapter Kengetallen E-20 NVI. Accessed Feb. 11, 2025. https://www.cooperatie-crv.nl/wp-content/uploads/2018/10/E_20-NVI_aug2018_en.pdf.
- CRV. 2022. NVI 2022: Updated Breeding Goals. Accessed Feb. 11, 2025. <https://www.cooperatie-crv.nl/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/186-22-blog-fokdoel-NVI-AEU-ENG-april-2022-150dpi.pdf>.
- CRV. 2024. Selection Indicators. e-Chapter 20, NVI. Accessed Nov. 2, 2025. https://www.cooperatie-crv.nl/wp-content/uploads/2024/08/E_20-NVI-Augustus-2024-Engels.pdf.
- Daetwyler, H., B. Villanueva, P. Bijma, and J. Woolliams. 2007. Inbreeding in genome-wide selection. *J. Anim. Breed. Genet.* 124:369–376. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-0388.2007.00693.x>.
- de Roos, A. P. W., C. Schrooten, R. F. Veerkamp, and J. A. M. van Arendonk. 2011. Effects of genomic selection on genetic improvement, inbreeding, and merit of young versus proven bulls. *J. Dairy Sci.* 94:1559–1567. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2010-3354>.
- Doekes, H. P. 2020. Genomic characterization and conservation of genetic diversity in cattle. Wageningen University.
- Doekes, H. P., P. Bijma, and J. J. Windig. 2021. How depressing is inbreeding? A meta-analysis of 30 years of research on the effects of inbreeding in livestock. *Genes (Basel)* 12:926. <https://doi.org/10.3390/genes12060926>.
- Doekes, H. P., R. F. Veerkamp, P. Bijma, G. de Jong, S. J. Hiemstra, and J. J. Windig. 2019. Inbreeding depression due to recent and ancient inbreeding in Dutch Holstein–Friesian dairy cattle. *Genet. Sel. Evol.* 51:54. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12711-019-0497-z>.
- Doekes, H. P., R. F. Veerkamp, P. Bijma, S. J. Hiemstra, and J. J. Windig. 2018. Trends in genome-wide and region-specific genetic diversity in the Dutch–Flemish Holstein–Friesian breeding program from 1986 to 2015. *Genet. Sel. Evol.* 50:15. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12711-018-0385-y>.
- Doublet, A.-C., P. Croiseau, S. Fritz, A. Michenet, C. Hozé, C. Danchin-Burge, D. Laloë, and G. Restoux. 2019. The impact of genomic selection on genetic diversity and genetic gain in three French dairy cattle breeds. *Genet. Sel. Evol.* 51:52. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12711-019-0495-1>.
- Eurogenomics. Eurogenomics MD. Accessed Oct. 2, 2025. <https://www.eurogenomics.com/actualites/the-eurog-md:-a-unique-genotyping-microarray-for-cattle-.html>.
- Eynard, S. E., P. Croiseau, D. Laloë, S. Fritz, M. P. L. Calus, and G. Restoux. 2018a. Which individuals to choose to update the reference population? Minimizing the loss of genetic diversity in animal genomic selection programs. *G3 (Bethesda)* 8:113–121. <https://doi.org/10.1534/g3.117.11117>.
- Eynard, S. E., J. J. Windig, S. J. Hiemstra, and M. P. L. Calus. 2016. Whole-genome sequence data uncover loss of genetic diversity due to selection. *Genet. Sel. Evol.* 48:33. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12711-016-0210-4>.
- Eynard, S. E., J. J. Windig, I. Hulsege, S.-J. Hiemstra, and M. P. L. Calus. 2018b. The impact of using old germplasm on genetic merit and diversity—A cattle breed case study. *J. Anim. Breed. Genet.* 135:311–322. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jbg.12333>.
- Falconer, D. S., and T. F. C. Mackay. 1996. *Introduction to Quantitative Genetics*. Harlow Pearson Education Limited.
- FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations). 2000. *Secondary Guidelines for Development of National Farm Animal Genetic Resources Management Plans: Management of Small Populations at Risk*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
- FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations). 2025. *Domestic Animal Diversity Information System*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. Accessed Jun. 20, 2025. <https://www.fao.org/dad-is/en/>.
- Forutan, M., S. Ansari Mahyari, C. Baes, N. Melzer, F. S. Schenkel, and M. Sargolzaei. 2018. Inbreeding and runs of homozygosity before and after genomic selection in North American Holstein cattle. *BMC Genomics* 19:98. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12864-018-4453-z>.
- García-Ruiz, A., J. B. Cole, P. M. VanRaden, G. R. Wiggans, F. J. Ruiz-López, and C. P. Van Tassell. 2016. Changes in genetic selection differentials and generation intervals in US Holstein dairy cattle as a result of genomic selection. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 113:E3995–E4004. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1519061113>.
- Gomez Proto, G., E. Mancin, C. Sartori, and R. Mantovani. 2024. Unraveling inbreeding patterns and selection signals in Alpine Grey cattle. *Animal* 18:101159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.animal.2024.101159>.
- Guinan, F. L., G. R. Wiggans, H. D. Norman, J. W. Dürr, J. B. Cole, C. P. Van Tassell, I. Misztal, and D. Lourenco. 2023. Changes in genetic trends in US dairy cattle since the implementation of genomic selection. *J. Dairy Sci.* 106:1110–1129. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2022-22205>.
- Hayes, B. J., H. A. Lewin, and M. E. Goddard. 2013. The future of livestock breeding: Genomic selection for efficiency, reduced emissions intensity, and adaptation. *Trends Genet.* 29:206–214. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tig.2012.11.009>.
- Hiemstra, S. J., and Y. de Haas. 2004. MRY. Accessed. https://www.regionalcattlebreeds.eu/publications/documents/5384_mrij%20koeien_engels.pdf.
- Hiemstra, S. J., Y. De Haas, A. Mäki-Tanila, and G. Gandini. 2010. *Page in Local Cattle Breeds in Europe: Development of Policies and Strategies for Self-Sustaining Breeds*. Wageningen Academic Publishers.
- Howard, J. T., J. E. Pryce, C. Baes, and C. Maltecca. 2017. Invited review: Inbreeding in the genomics era: Inbreeding, inbreeding depression, and management of genomic variability. *J. Dairy Sci.* 100:6009–6024. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2017-12787>.
- Institut de l'Élevage. 2018. *Indexation Bovine Laitière*. Accessed Nov. 10, 2025. https://idele.fr/fileadmin/user_upload/IBL2018-1_Base_isuTA2.pdf.
- Institut de l'Élevage. 2022. *Dispositif Génétique*. Accessed Feb. 23, 2025. <https://idele.fr/detail-article/dispositif-genetique-chiffre-cles-ruminants-2022>.
- Interbull Centre. 2024. *National genomic evaluation forms provided by countries*. Accessed Aug. 3, 2024. <https://interbull.org/ib-nationalgenofoms>.
- Jacques, A., G. Leroy, X. Rognon, E. Verrier, M. Tixier-Boichard, and G. Restoux. 2023. Reintroducing genetic diversity in populations from cryopreserved material: The case of Abondance, a French local dairy cattle breed. *Genet. Sel. Evol.* 55:28. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12711-023-00801-6>.

- Keller, M. C., P. M. Visscher, and M. E. Goddard. 2011. Quantification of inbreeding due to distant ancestors and its detection using dense single nucleotide polymorphism data. *Genetics* 189:237–249. <https://doi.org/10.1534/genetics.111.130922>.
- Lillehammer, M., T. H. E. Meuwissen, and A. K. Sonesson. 2011. A comparison of dairy cattle breeding designs that use genomic selection. *J. Dairy Sci.* 94:493–500. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2010-3518>.
- Lozada-Soto, E. A., C. Maltecca, D. Lu, S. Miller, J. B. Cole, and F. Tiezzi. 2021. Trends in genetic diversity and the effect of inbreeding in American Angus cattle under genomic selection. *Genet. Sel. Evol.* 53:50. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12711-021-00644-z>.
- Lozada-Soto, E. A., F. Tiezzi, J. Jiang, J. B. Cole, P. M. VanRaden, and C. Maltecca. 2022. Genomic characterization of autozygosity and recent inbreeding trends in all major breeds of US dairy cattle. *J. Dairy Sci.* 105:8956–8971. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2022-22116>.
- Ma, L., J. R. O'Connell, P. M. VanRaden, B. Shen, A. Padhi, C. Sun, D. M. Bickhart, J. B. Cole, J. F. Null, G. E. Liu, Y. Da, and G. R. Wiggans. 2015. Cattle sex-specific recombination and genetic control from a large pedigree analysis. *PLoS Genet.* 11:e1005387. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pgen.1005387>.
- Maignel, L., D. Boichard, and E. Verrier. 1996. Genetic variability of French dairy breeds estimated from pedigree information. *Interbull Bull.* 14:49–54.
- Makanjuola, B. O., F. Miglior, E. A. Abdalla, C. Maltecca, F. S. Schenkel, and C. F. Baes. 2020. Effect of genomic selection on rate of inbreeding and coancestry and effective population size of Holstein and Jersey cattle populations. *J. Dairy Sci.* 103:5183–5199. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2019-18013>.
- McQuillan, R., A.-L. Leutenegger, R. Abdel-Rahman, C. S. Franklin, M. Pericic, L. Barac-Lauc, N. Smolej-Narancic, B. Janicijevic, O. Polasek, A. Tenesa, A. K. Macleod, S. M. Farrington, P. Rudan, C. Hayward, V. Vitart, I. Rudan, S. H. Wild, M. G. Dunlop, A. F. Wright, H. Campbell, and J. F. Wilson. 2008. Runs of homozygosity in European populations. *Am. J. Hum. Genet.* 83:359–372. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajhg.2008.08.007>.
- Meuwissen, T., B. Hayes, and M. Goddard. 2013. Accelerating improvement of livestock with genomic selection. *Annu. Rev. Anim. Biosci.* 1:221–237. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-animal-031412-103705>.
- Meuwissen, T., B. Hayes, and M. Goddard. 2016. Genomic selection: A paradigm shift in animal breeding. *Anim. Front.* 6:6–14. <https://doi.org/10.2527/af.2016-0002>.
- Meuwissen, T. H. 1997. Maximizing the response of selection with a predefined rate of inbreeding. *J. Anim. Sci.* 75:934. <https://doi.org/10.2527/1997.754934x>.
- Meuwissen, T. H. E. 2023. Gghatvr4. Accessed Nov. 3, 2025. <https://github.com/theomeuwissen/gghatvr4>.
- Meuwissen, T. H. E., B. J. Hayes, and M. E. Goddard. 2001. Prediction of total genetic value using genome-wide dense marker maps. *Genetics* 157:1819–1829. <https://doi.org/10.1093/genetics/157.4.1819>.
- Meuwissen, T. H. E., and Z. Luo. 1992. Computing inbreeding coefficients in large populations. *Genet. Sel. Evol.* 24:305. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1297-9686-24-4-305>.
- Meuwissen, T. H. E., and J. K. Oldenbroek. 2017. Chapter 5. Management of genetic diversity including genomic selection in small in vivo populations. Brill.
- Misztal, I., and D. Lourenco. 2024. Potential negative effects of genomic selection. *J. Anim. Sci.* 102:skae155. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jas/skae155>.
- Nejati-Javaremi, A., C. Smith, and J. P. Gibson. 1997. Effect of total allelic relationship on accuracy of evaluation and response to selection. *J. Anim. Sci.* 75:1738–1745. <https://doi.org/10.2527/1997.7571738x>.
- Norwegian Red. 2025. The Norwegian Estimated Breeding Values (EBVs). Accessed. <https://www.norwegianred.com/about-norwegian-red/norwegian-ebvs/>.
- Organisme de sélection de la Race Vosgienne. Effectifs et localisation - La Race Bovine Vosgienne. Accessed Aug. 25, 2025. <https://www.racevosgienne.com/race/presentation-de-la-race/effectifs-et-localisation>.
- Pérez-Enciso, M. 1995. Use of the uncertain relationship matrix to compute effective population size. *J. Anim. Breed. Genet.* 112:327–332. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-0388.1995.tb00574.x>.
- Pryce, J. E., and H. D. Daetwyler. 2012. Designing dairy cattle breeding schemes under genomic selection: A review of international research. *Anim. Prod. Sci.* 52:107–114. <https://doi.org/10.1071/AN11098>.
- Pryce, J. E., M. Haile-Mariam, M. E. Goddard, and B. J. Hayes. 2014. Identification of genomic regions associated with inbreeding depression in Holstein and Jersey dairy cattle. *Genet. Sel. Evol.* 46:71. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12711-014-0071-7>.
- Rochus, C. M., C. F. Price, and I. Pocrnić. 2025. Review: Assessing available genetic diversity estimates of rare breeds of livestock. *Animal* 19:101669. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.animal.2025.101669>.
- Sargolzaei, M., J. P. Chesnais, and F. S. Schenkel. 2014. A new approach for efficient genotype imputation using information from relatives. *BMC Genomics* 15:478. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2164-15-478>.
- Sargolzaei, M., H. Iwaisaki, and J.-J. Colleau. 2005. A fast algorithm for computing inbreeding coefficients in large populations. *J. Anim. Breed. Genet.* 122:325–331. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-0388.2005.00538.x>.
- Sarviaho, K., P. Uimari, and K. Martikainen. 2023. Estimating inbreeding rate and effective population size in the Finnish Ayrshire population in the era of genomic selection. *J. Anim. Breed. Genet.* 140:343–353. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jbg.12762>.
- Schaeffer, L. R. 2006. Strategy for applying genome-wide selection in dairy cattle. *J. Anim. Breed. Genet.* 123:218–223. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-0388.2006.00595.x>.
- Scott, B. A., M. Haile-Mariam, B. G. Cocks, and J. E. Pryce. 2021. How genomic selection has increased rates of genetic gain and inbreeding in the Australian national herd, genomic information nucleus, and bulls. *J. Dairy Sci.* 104:11832–11849. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2021-20326>.
- Sonesson, A. K., J. A. Woolliams, and T. H. E. Meuwissen. 2012. Genomic selection requires genomic control of inbreeding. *Genet. Sel. Evol.* 44:27. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1297-9686-44-27>.
- Speed, D., and D. J. Balding. 2015. Relatedness in the post-genomic era: is it still useful? *Nat. Rev. Genet.* 16:33–44. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrg3821>.
- Stoop, M., G. Veninga, G. de Jong, and F. Reinhardt. 2017. Genomics in small populations: The MRY breed. *Interbull Bull.* 51:26–28.
- Topolski, P., and W. Jagusiak. 2020. Inbreeding in a population of Polish Holstein-Friesian young bulls before and after genomic selection. *Ann. Anim. Sci.* 20:71–83. <https://doi.org/10.2478/aoas-2019-0065>.
- Van Eenennaam, A. L., K. A. Weigel, A. E. Young, M. A. Cleveland, and J. C. M. Dekkers. 2014. Applied animal genomics: Results from the field. *Annu. Rev. Anim. Biosci.* 2:105–139. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-animal-022513-114119>.
- VanRaden, P. M. 2008. Efficient methods to compute genomic predictions. *J. Dairy Sci.* 91:4414–4423. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2007-0980>.
- Wellmann, R. 2019. Optimum contribution selection for animal breeding and conservation: The R package optiSel. *BMC Bioinformatics* 20:25. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12859-018-2450-5>.
- Wiggans, G. R., J. B. Cole, S. M. Hubbard, and T. S. Sonstegard. 2017. Genomic selection in dairy cattle: The USDA experience. *Annu. Rev. Anim. Biosci.* 5:309–327. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-animal-021815-111422>.
- Windig, J. J., and I. Hulsegge. 2021. Retriever and Pointer: Software to evaluate inbreeding and genetic management in captive populations. *Animals (Basel)* 11:1332. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani11051332>.

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